

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12598416>

Abstract. This art about the grammatical, lexical and phonetic coicle is about teaching methods in English classes. The article talks mponents of speech. The article also suggests methods for developing oral speech.

Key words: language, discourse, style, technology, skill, competence.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ МЕТОДОВ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. Это искусство о грамматической, лексической и фонетической связке — о методах преподавания на уроках английского языка. В статье рассматриваются компоненты речи. Также в статье предложены методы развития устной речи.

Ключевые слова: язык, дискурс, стиль, технология, умение, компетентность.

Nowadays, education in Uzbekistan is at the beginning of its own period of development is forgiving This peculiarity is, first of all, the nationalization of the content of education, that is, the national tradition of our very rich past history, culture, science, language, which has a very beautiful, high human moral content. We are fortunate to educate the young generation who are the future of our society based on our customs. it requires us to approach the educational process in a new way, to use new methods and content, forms and tools. New tasks cannot be accomplished with the old method. Therefore, we think that this issue is a new pedagogical technology can be implemented on the basis of. Each type of speech activity has its own difficulties. Difficulties in listening comprehension are numerous. Knowing them is one of the decisive conditions for teaching a foreign language. The problems of perception, including the perceptual understanding of speech, have been elaborated in world psychology. The science of foreign language teaching methodology effectively uses existing theoretical considerations. Difficulties in the field of listening comprehension of students in school conditions include:

1. Formal language difficulties. It becomes difficult to listen and understand words (homophones) with different meanings and similar sounds (homophones) or passive voice of a foreign language. Homophones and passive verbs seem familiar at first glance, but the trick is making it difficult to discern the content of the audio text.

2. Content difficulties. What, where, who in the coverage of the received information There are difficulties in perceiving evidence such as with, when, or making connections between them, as well as general ideas.

3. Difficulties in the conditions of speech perception. Of these, it is enough to mention the speed, tone and complexity of mechanically recorded audio text. At the same time, it is natural that there is a gap in the understanding of the auditory text once, listening to a stranger, the uniqueness of the voice.

4. Difficulties related to the form of speech. It is difficult for the student to respond in a dialog speech, and to remember the sentences while listening to a monologue.

5. Difficulties that occur from the point of view of linguistics. They are called linguistic - lexical, grammatical and phonetic difficulties. Paired concepts in the lexicon (for example, words representing aspects of the world, polysemy (polysemy), word meaning in stable combinations, auxiliary words, grammatically non-native phenomena or phonetic sharp variation in writing and pronunciation, accent and tone dissimilarity caused corresponding difficulties.

6. Difficulties related to the structure of the audio text. It has been found that the structure of the audio text (compositional - content structure) also causes difficulties. Because he has a direct interest in learning the information presented. Logical cohesion of the sentence or the beginning of the line, surface or depth of the text, participation of unfamiliar lexical units and a number of similar compositional-content situations are factors that determine the level of comprehension of the audio text.

The purpose of recognizing the difficulties a student faces in listening comprehension is to take steps to prevent them. Challenges require work and time, and require special exercises.

Educational process by timely elimination (neutralization) of difficulties acceleration and development of the most suitable (optimal) methodology of training.

Difficulties that occur in language learning or in life in general are determined by cause and effect. Difficulties can be identified in advance, its causes can be known. The emergence of difficulty is determined by various errors and the level of achievement of the intended result. Correct formation of the psychophysiological mechanisms of listening comprehension is of great importance in order to overcome the difficulties of students' ability to perceive the speech of others and understand its content.

Teaching oral speech is one of the main practical goals of teaching a foreign language in high school. High school graduates are able to give oral information and communicate in a foreign language, depending on the topic studied. they have to listen to the speech and understand it. First of all, it is necessary to mention the problem of the unity of learning oral speech.

Previously, lexical and grammatical elements were considered separately as the material of oral speech, but now, based on the achievements of modern linguistics, there is an opportunity to consider the issue as complex units consisting of a unity of grammatical, lexical and phonetic components of speech. Then there are the preparatory exercises aimed at learning such complex units, the types of these exercises, their importance in the teaching of oral speech and the mummy system. The issue of speech exercises, which ensure the development of the skills of using the learned language material in a speech situation, is more complicated. The effort to create an atmosphere of natural speech problems in the classroom leads to distinguish between dialogic and monologic oral speech problems, as well as separate teaching and another aspect of oral speech, the perception of the interlocutor as a special transfer of speech. Oral speech occurs under certain conditions, and these conditions affect the nature of the speech. These conditions are extralinguistic / extralinguistic. They include the situation in which the speech activity takes place, the environment, the age and level of growth of the speaker, the topic of the conversation, attention to the perception of the listener's speech, facial expressions, gestures, and others. All these factors play an active role primarily in dialogic speech, and to some extent in monologic speech. Verbal nutty style is characterized by laughter from the outside of the swimmer, expressing different reactions to various influences, introductions and endings, for example: oh, how glad I am to see

you! The style of oral speech differs from the style of written speech by the conciseness of the expression or, as it is often said, "situation". This is the perspective in which the swimmers are standing in the process of oral communication. It is possible to include (1) the process of expressing an opinion, (2) speaking, (3) oral communication, (4) the result of the expression of an opinion in the scope of the methodological concept of verbal communication. Teaching students to speak a foreign language is considered practical, that is, during the first few (about three) years of education, they learn speaking and listening comprehension.

In English, we express actions with verbs. There are independent and auxiliary verbs in English. An English language learner must know auxiliary verbs

necessary. One of the auxiliary verbs is the verb to have. The verb to have is translated into Uzbek as an independent verb. It has two forms: (Simple Present) – have/has. Have for all persons, and has for the 3rd person singular, for the past tense (Simple Past) – had, for the future tense (Simple Future) – shall have, will have.

The quality and effectiveness of the lesson will not depend on a multi-page structured lesson plan. In the plan, the actions that will be implemented, who, what and when to implement them, although the time of each action is divided into seconds, no matter how much effort and time is spent on preparing for the lesson, it is possible to be satisfied with the lesson and not achieve the intended goal. Sometimes a well-crafted lesson plan can be turned upside down, leaving the teacher feeling like they are teaching in an empty classroom. The teaching process is very complicated, and the teacher must take into account many pedagogical factors: what part of the day the lesson takes place, whether it is in the first hours or the last hours, when the student's brain is not tired: the complexity of the subject matter is normal; the role of students in the formation of independent knowledge of this topic, etc. Therefore, the teacher should always face the following problems.

1. Why is the lesson different?
2. Why are the results of the lessons different?
3. Why does a particular lesson excel in one learning group and fail or fail in another?

Even the teacher himself can behave differently in different classes, they become unrecognizable, like other people. The lesson is creativity, but creativity is creativity not only for the teacher, but also for the student. Failure of the student to actively participate in the lesson will result in the lesson failing.

of students as a result of using innovative methods in English classes
logical thinking skills develop, speech becomes fluent, quick and correct answer
the ability to give is formed. Such methods make the student eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process.

Teaching monologue and dialogue in a foreign language is one of the main requirements of the curriculum.

One more thing to pay attention to is social work, complete freedom, does not mean that I will do whatever I want. Creative work cannot deny control and management of methodological or theoretical determination of certain issues of education. This should not be replaced by templating. Creating conditions for creative work, managing and directing this process is important.

Studying the characteristics of professional activities shows that any activity can be at the level of art or technology.

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